

CITY-MOVE

City based interventions to stimulate active movement for health

HORIZON-HLTH-2023-DISEASE-03

D(4.2): Guidance document on data management practices

De Deurwaerder, O. - UA

Thornton, L. - UA

Correa, J.C. - FUJNC

Summary Sheet

Deliverable Number	D4.2
Deliverable Name	Guidance document on routine-data practices
Full Project Title	CITY-MOVE: City based interventions to stimulate active movement for health
Responsible Author(s)	De Deurwaerder, Oberon Thornton, Lukar Correa, Juan Carlos
Contributing Partner(s)	UA, FUJNC
Peer Review	/
Contractual Delivery Date	31-12-2024
Actual Delivery Date	23-12-2024
Status	Final
Dissemination level	PU
Version	V1.1
No. of Pages	16
WP/Task related to the deliverable	WP 4 / Task 4.2
WP/Task responsible	UA, Lukar Thornton
Document ID	CITY_MOVE_D4.2_Routine_data_guidance
Abstract	Guidance document on routine data collection and management practices.

Legal Disclaimer

CITY-MOVE is funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or Horizon EU. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Table of Contents

Contents

Executive Summary	4
1. Overall.....	5
2. City-specific insights	7
2.1. Antwerp	7
2.2. Bogotá	9
2.3. Kampala	10
2.4. Lima	11
2.5. Ljubljana	13
2.6. Rotterdam	14

List of Tables

Table 1: Interviews per city as of 12th December 2024.....	6
--	---

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This second deliverable of the fourth work package for the City-Move project reports on the qualitative evaluation of routine data management in the six partner cities. The first deliverable aimed to provide a comprehensive overview of the data collected, their update frequency, and geographical granularity; we subsequently attempted to understand the underlying dynamics and practices of collecting, managing, publishing, and using this data. Interviews were conducted with different policy stakeholders in each city, providing insights from different perspectives in the city governments. We formulated an overview of the key insights in each city, highlighted strengths, identified challenges, and formulated possible recommendations for improving the current situation based on what we have learned in the interviews.

As outside observers, we hope that our cross-examination of best practices might improve evidence-based decision-making in all areas influencing physical activity (PA) behaviour in the urban environment. Key challenges arising in all cities evolve around four central topics. A first recurring theme is a fluent exchange of collected data, as existing information is often kept by the collector of the information and only shared on request if shared at all. A second common issue is the suboptimal use of existing data because of privacy and legal considerations, which are often more technically rather than ethically complicated. Thirdly, gains can be made by improving data collection methods, often with tailored adaptations in each city, ranging from better use of existing infrastructure to directly sourcing information from the urban population. A last recurring issue is that, in many cases, more substantial leadership initiatives are needed to connect the dots or to organization-wide carry the incentive for changing existing practices.

The number of interviews varies per city, and we aim to continue the analysis in key areas in the following year, bringing together the data mapping of the first deliverable as well as the insights from the interviews as of today as well as those in the following months in the planned process evaluation paper on the work done in the fourth work package.

1. OVERALL

1.1. Introduction

City environments can play a role in the prevalence of non-communicable diseases (NCDs) through several intersecting social, cultural, and environmental factors. Cities are thus both a threat to health and a potential enabler of change. Given the untapped potential of cities to promote PA, CITY-MOVE focuses on adapting the GAPPA to the city level (city-GAPPA).

CITY-MOVE aims to accelerate and support action for PA at the city level in six cities across three continents: Europe (Antwerp, Ljubljana, and Rotterdam), Africa (Kampala) and Latin America (Bogota and Lima), to learn from cities in different phases and in diverse cultural and macro-economic contexts.

In the fourth work package of City-Move, we aim to map existing administrative data sources and understand data management practices in each partner city. Following the routine data mapping conducted in the first half of 2024, which was updated since its dissemination, we will share the insights acquired from our investigative efforts and a set of semi-structured interviews in this document. These interviews bring a qualitative understanding of the practices, problems and background of each city's data collection and management practices.

1.2. Overview

Antwerp, Bogota, Kampala, Lima, Ljubljana, and Rotterdam, the six partner cities in the project, all vary significantly from each other in geographic, socio-economic and cultural context. The data landscape they operate in reflects this diversity. How these differences play out, as well as the specific opportunities and challenges each city faces, will be discussed in detail in the following sections. We would first like to highlight a couple of standard aspects that, based on our fieldwork, pose challenges for data managers and policymakers in all six cities. In short, these are summarized by:

1.2.1. Data exchange and publication

Most cities make efforts and investments to publicly share (part of) the data they collect and manage. They often face similar challenges in exchanging information within different parts of government, affecting the timely availability of the most recent information, bottlenecks in fluid throughflow of the latest numbers, and (perceived) inefficiency because of data-gatekeeping between organizational units. In the long run, a more structural framework in software architecture and data-sharing policy could improve these issues.

1.2.2. Privacy concerns and performance

In most cities, the interviewees highlighted the performance restrictions they experienced in dealing with privacy regulations. These affected their ability to acquire information in time, as often different judicial steps have to be taken to share information that is, in theory, commonly available across the different levels of government. Policymakers often mention the need for disaggregated micro-level data as a hindrance to crafting effective policies or making targeted decisions in their line of work.

1.2.3. Data collection methods

A third common challenge in all cities, though in varying forms, relates to data collection. In the cases we observed, data collection is often the most feasible, short-term challenge to tackle. Gains can be made by making better use of existing collection methods (Antwerp), connecting infrastructure (Ljubljana) and implementing digital contact possibilities with the city government (Kampala), to name a few.

1.2.4. Leadership initiatives

The interviewees often work in a relatively independent environment, where they have ownership and control over the information they collect, utilise and share with others. This is a strength, allowing them to acquire insights and make decisions about their specific tasks and responsibilities. However, it is a challenge in that a more overarching approach to data sharing and publication is needed to improve the structural level. Interviewees pointed to the lack of top-down initiatives to improve this matter. In other cities, we observed a strong top-down data-sharing and publication culture. With the right infrastructure investments, expertise within the respective departments, and a shift in thinking about data sharing, existing information can be put to much better use.

Table 1: Interviews per city as of 12th December 2024

City	Interviews conducted to date
Antwerp	5
Bogota	2
Kampala	3
Lima	1
Ljubljana	1
Rotterdam	5

2. CITY-SPECIFIC INSIGHTS

2.1. ANTWERP

2.1.1. Overview

In Antwerp, we interviewed five people working in the city government. They provided some essential insights into the routine-data practices of the city, both from the management as from the user perspective. In general, the interviewees were keen to be interviewed, and making contact was easy.

Two core architectural pillars dominate the routine-data landscape of Antwerp. The first one is “City in Maps”, a fully GIS-based platform combining geographic layers on a wide range of topics, from infrastructure, socio-economic indicators, open urban space, mobility and many more. All layers are publicly available in the web-environment and accessible through an API. This platform both sources and exports data to most of the departments within the city and is often consulted by different policy levels to provide information on request or bridge software gaps to exchange information automatically. For an external user, combining different layers or analysing the information provided must be done manually, not through the online platform.

The second pillar is “City in Numbers”, containing a wider variety of socio-economic indicators and combining data from the city and other levels of government. This platform aims to provide easy access and insights to policymakers and the public, as visual representations, trend analysis, and combination of (almost all) indicators on different geographic levels of aggregation are available in a plug-and-play manner. All indicators and reports are freely downloadable. The “City in Numbers” platform depends on internal sources and personal contact with e.g. the provincial level and the national bureau of statistics for keeping their information up to date.

Thirdly, some separate software platforms exist, containing more specific data on, for example, city infrastructure and activities, e.g. participation in sports or cultural events, a reservation system for city infrastructure, and an overview of civil society organisations, their activities and members. We interviewed the “Sporting A” department, which initially developed this platform, though it is now being used more broadly within the city government.

2.1.2. Strengths

- We note the vast amount of readily available, longitudinal and geographically detailed information published and shared by the different city platforms.
- There is a strong culture and sense of importance regarding data publication.
- There is a strong organisational drive to provide infrastructure and allow data-driven decision-making.
- Strong documentation of information through metadata.

2.1.3. Challenges

- Privacy and security seem to pose challenges for all interviewees. For the GIS-level, security updates are essential, though implementation is sometimes tricky. For the sports department, privacy concerns pose bottlenecks for crafting tailored policies for different target populations.
- Data managers and users have reported that software expertise is insufficient. “City in Numbers” spends much time explaining the information on their website or responding to specific requests for freely available datasets on their platform. The sporting department noted the complexity of the platform as a hindrance to effectively using it and mentioned a lack of qualitative understanding of the numbers as a restriction to implementing open data as performance indicators for their policy initiatives.
- For “City in Numbers”, personnel changes and interpersonal relations remain a key challenge to fluid performance and exchange of data as well.

2.1.4. Recommendations

- Further implementing metadata documentation practices across all available indicators. This kind of documentation exists for many indicators but not for all.
- Longitudinal compatibility can be challenging when long-running survey questions are updated, administrative boundaries are changed, or new metrics replace old indicators. Involving stakeholders from all levels in making these decisions can improve data availability and comparability.
- Optimising the use of city smart cards (A-Kaart) to improve primary data collection on citizen interactions. The infrastructure exists (readers, cards, web portal) and could improve administrative efficiency (e.g. for sports activities, a paper attendance form is still often used, creating an administrative workload of inputting names and numbers by staff manning the city infrastructure). Implementing this can be a low-cost way of standardising data collection in an easy-to-access, fast manner.
- For analysis of urban form and the effects of infrastructure improvements, there is an opportunity for “City in Maps”, the GIS-level, to publish longitudinal datasets. These older versions exist and are kept but unavailable to the public.

2.2. BOGOTÁ

2.2.1. Overview

Bogotá, the city with the largest population in the City-Move project, boasts a strong institutional culture of publishing routine data. The city runs its open-data platform, covering more than ten thousand datasets. These contain data on urban infrastructure, socio-economic variables, transportation, governmental budget, health and environmental factors. As highlighted in the interviews, the city government champions the publication of anonymous microdata and open data portals, offering transparency and availability of information for policymakers and the public and a strong statistical capacity, transferring the open data culture into informed decision-making.

We had the opportunity to interview a representative from an NGO working on quality of life and a representative from a national health organization working country-wide. Both interviewees demonstrated the aforementioned open data culture as a strong facilitator of their work. From our research and analysis of the governmental platforms, we note the room for improvement in structuring the data published online (e.g., ensuring conformity in naming datasets), allowing for better findability and usage. There were gaps in data coverage in some instances, with specific years missing. As all datasets were pooled without specific comments from the publishers, providing more metadata could further strengthen existing practices.

Given the sheer size of the government and the language barriers for the European team, getting in the room with representatives of the relevant ministries to conduct our research proved challenging sometimes. We plan on continuing our interview series in collaboration with the Colombian colleagues in 2025 to better understand the inter-departmental dynamics.

2.2.2. Strengths

- Easy access, strong and abundant open data culture on various subjects from different governmental bodies.
- Commitment to Open Data by publicly accessible microdata and investing in interactive data portals, fostering transparency and civic engagement.
- Strong open data is accompanied by different specialized organizations that provide readymade insights and reports on various topics related to the quality of life in Bogotá.

2.2.3. Challenges

- The update frequency of datasets varies among different publishers.
- Strong survey landscape, although the practice of anonymised microdata is not implemented across all different questionnaires, reducing granularity.
- Inconsistency in metadata practices undermines the value of published data.

2.2.4. Recommendations

- Ensure timely updates of the latest information through structured guidelines.
- Standardize metadata practices regarding naming datasets and providing context on included indicators.

2.3. KAMPALA

2.3.1. Overview

In Kampala, we interviewed three city officials from the transport, public health and urban planning directorates. The interviews provided insights into developments over the past decade and highlighted current challenges in managing the city's rapid expansion. A shared priority among interviewees is improving infrastructure. Road safety remains a pressing issue, impacting urban life and influencing behaviour. With the city heavily investing in basic infrastructure, there are opportunities to promote pedestrian-friendly, sustainable urban development.

The lack of public transportation makes most longer-distance travel reliant on motorized transport, resulting in traffic congestion and increasing the appeal of motorcycles and moto-taxis. The dependence on motorised vehicles worsens air quality, undermining the health benefits of active transportation. Poor infrastructure makes longer walking or cycling trips impractical, as sidewalks and cycling lanes are scarce. Rapid urbanisation leads to citizens building illegal or non-authorized structures, making it difficult for the city government to assess where infrastructure expansion is needed, i.e., identifying emerging population centres.

Accurate and accessible data is essential for effective policymaking. Since 2012, the city's geographic information system (GIS) unit has digitalized large volumes of records, transforming paper files into accessible digital data. The GIS unit has supported multiple directorates by providing critical information for various policies. However, digitalization progresses issue by issue, driven by immediate policy needs rather than a structured strategy. The city is improving data collection by using standardized digital forms for field teams and launching initiatives to collect input from citizens, such as reporting infrastructure issues or illegal construction.

Despite these advancements, a significant challenge is the gatekeeping culture between directorates, where data is treated as proprietary. This pattern restricts the flow of information, hampers the integration of datasets, and limits the effectiveness of city-wide policy initiatives.

2.3.2. Strengths

- Innovative strategies for data collection (digital forms, input from social media).
- A strong GIS department that provides the foundational framework for integrating datasets across directorates.

2.3.3. Challenges

- All interviewees mention budget shortages as a barrier to effective policymaking.
- Gatekeeping culture of datasets, no widespread support for sharing information.
- Reactive, problem-driven policymaking, lacking a structured, top-down approach to set priorities.

2.3.4. Recommendations

- More competencies (and budget) to the GIS division, as they function as a central data pillar for all directorates.
- Implementation of a directorate-wide, top-down policy incentive to change the culture of proprietary data practices.
- Creation of a repository of all partners of government (universities, NGOs, ...) to centralize different data sources (e.g. health surveys, air quality information, ...).

2.4. LIMA

2.4.1. Overview

Lima has proven to be a more challenging case for which to retrieve insights. Reaching out to city officials has been slow due to internal political conflicts, resulting in a prolonged strike among the city civil servants. There are restrictions when trying to access governmental websites from outside of Peru, an observation we could later confirm in the interview. This interviewee provided valuable insights, however, into the city's routine-data practices, particularly regarding challenges in coordination and data use across departments.

Nation-wide, Peru has an open data publication system comparable to the one from Colombia, on which more than ten thousand datasets on a wide range of topics are available. Looking specifically at the city, Lima's data landscape is fragmented, with individual municipalities collecting and managing their own data. Certain organisations such as the Metropolitan Environmental System, do collect data across the metropolitan area. Collaboration across departments is limited, and no centralised internal system exists to integrate or share

information. Some datasets, such as those for transport and mobility, are collected but not consistently used for policymaking.

Furthermore, each new administration brings about a profound change in staff, who all need time to acquaint themselves with current processes and software. The changing cabinet leads to repeated cavities in expertise, posing barriers to the effective use of data for urban planning and decision-making. We aim to further investigate this in subsequent interviews in 2025.

2.4.2. Strengths

- Some datasets, especially in transport and mobility, are collected regularly.
- Individual departments have strong ownership of their data collection processes.
- Many city datasets are published on the national platform, signalling a strong institutionalised drive to publish information.

2.4.3. Challenges

- Absence of a centralised internal platform or strategy for data integration.
- Limited interdepartmental collaboration on data use and sharing.
- Gaps in technical expertise for managing and analysing routine data, partly due to frequent personnel changes and non-continuity of management.
- Datasets published in online platforms are not grouped or structured, reducing their utility.

2.4.4. Recommendations

- Develop a centralised platform to integrate and share data across municipality departments instead of directly pushing to the national platform.
- Create a legal framework to standardise data management practices.
- Invest in training municipal staff to improve technical skills in data analysis and use.

2.5. LJUBLJANA

2.5.1. Overview

In Ljubljana, the city with the smallest population in City-Move, we had the opportunity to interview the head of the department for digitalisation, providing an in-depth and historical overview of data collection and management practices. The city disbanded its internal statistics bureau in 2016, resulting in the decentralisation of information about the city and its residents, in which different departments became proprietors of their data. From then on, numbers were no longer generally published in their raw format, with insights hidden in yearly reports published by the respective departments. The discontinuation of the statistics bureau, therefore, in the first place, meant a reduction in efficiency and data-driven decision-making, as information is currently manually exchanged across the city departments.

Opportunities arose, however, as the newly founded digitalisation department had to make do with the assets at hand. With the availability of the many highly qualitative metrics the city collects on traffic volumes, cycling behaviour, air quality, and temperature, but in the absence of an overarching central platform to collect and publish them, the need for a structured approach was evident. The city is exploring the concept of a “data mesh” as a solution and has been planning its implementation step-by-step. The city has many strengths to play on, such as two locally run data centres, investments in Internet of Things sensors and a self-designed online platform monitoring infrastructure developments over the past years and hourly traffic information. Their new policy aims to have ready-made data products, updated continuously in fixed intervals, that offer easy access to evidence supporting policy decisions. The first project that is currently underway is on air quality data.

The biggest challenges in Ljubljana arise from budget shortages. Slovenian municipalities do not receive a separate digitalisation budget and rely on the national government for funding. The technology and know-how exist, but the lack of budget refrains the city from hiring software developers and data specialists. A top-down decision from the national government to support the local municipalities and formally vest the digitalisation agenda in policy seems necessary to fundamentally change this. Ljubljana could be a great example to prove the usefulness of this matter with its pragmatic and hands-on approach.

2.5.2. Strengths

- The city boasts strong infrastructural foundations for its digital future, both in data collection (network of various sensors) and hosting (Ljubljana has two data centres of its own).
- The vision for its digital infrastructure (data mesh architecture) is clear and is being implemented pragmatically and step-by-step.
- No reliance on external software providers, as what is currently done is self-written using mostly open-source standards.
- Close-knit relationship with the national statistics bureau, offering opportunities for long-term solutions.

2.5.3. Challenges

- Know-how among policy stakeholders in using existing platforms is limited.
- There is an urgent need for more coherence in data management practices in the city. A meta-catalogue of the available datasets is necessary, but making this a policy priority is challenging as it requires the involvement of all different departments.
- Unstructured ownership of infrastructure, as it is not always clear who installed or manages Internet of Things sensors.

2.5.4. Recommendations

- The most important short-term improvement seems to be finding a solution for the meta-catalogue problem, as this will be the foundation for future restructuring (to be able to organize data, the city needs to understand what data they collect) and can directly benefit evidence-based policymaking even without any other changes made.
- Displaying the usefulness of the proposed data products pragmatically, convincing other departments to get involved (“leading by example”).
- As budget decisions are made on the national level, the good relationship with the National Statistics Bureau seems like a possible pathway to change policy on the local level.

2.6. ROTTERDAM

2.6.1. Overview

The five interviewees in Rotterdam provided a comprehensive overview of data management roles in the city. Their perspectives ranged from high-level architectural views to hands-on, bottom-up data use, making Rotterdam an intriguing case. The city has a strong, institutionally embedded culture of collecting and sharing diverse data, though opportunities for improvement remain. Through the “GAIA” project, Rotterdam is pioneering a novel approach to integrate all city data into a singular ecosystem. GAIA aims to streamline data sharing via differentiated access rights for users, starting from the premise that all city data is fundamentally shared information across government levels. For instance, while police require sensitive citizen data (e.g., criminal records), urban planners only need aggregated population statistics. Traditionally, this necessitates separate databases and manual dataset exchanges. GAIA will centralize data in one system, where organizations retain editing rights corresponding to their capacity, with system-wide updates. Benefits include reduced infrastructure and personnel costs, up-to-date data, and faster policy decisions. The GAIA architecture has been in development for three years and is slated for rollout by 2027.

Currently, a few notable aspects stand out. The central research and business intelligence unit, OBI, offers a central database akin to Antwerp’s “Stad in Cijfers,” using the ADF Swing-viewer platform. Budget cuts will pose challenges but also opportunities for efficiency. OBI’s manual database updates, often reliant on importing Excel files, can be significantly improve with automation and APIs. Other departments also use the ADF Swing-

viewer, each managing their data independently. Closer collaboration or centralizing data could reduce software licensing costs and allow staff to focus on research rather than responding to requests for (already publicly available) information.

The “Neighbourhood Atlas” (Wijk Atlas) exemplifies bottom-up innovation. Started by a neighbourhood planner who secured cross-departmental funding, it optimizes city planning at the local level. Integration of datasets and policy objectives addresses inefficiencies such as uncoordinated infrastructural improvements that cause prolonged disruptions. In the first project, gathering data took five months and relied on their personal networks. Integrating these data sources and rolling out the Wijk Atlas framework citywide presents a significant opportunity.

Lastly, we note the heavy reliance of the different interviewees on surveys. All interviewees mentioned a decline in response rates due to survey fatigue, causing limited generalisability of their results. Here again, a more integrated approach across departments sending out surveys could help tackle this problem, avoiding overlap in questionnaires and protecting willingness to participate in the city population.

2.6.2. Strengths

- Specialized research unit in touch with different departments of the city government.
- Adaptive surveys allow for rotation of research topics depending on policy objectives.
- Most comprehensive long-term strategy of partner cities so far (GAIA).
- Pathway for the medium term: “Wijkatlas” project, integrating different datasets to create a holistic policy objective perspective for a given district.

2.6.3. Challenges

- The throughflow of datasets is often complicated and dependent on interpersonal connections (e.g. it took Wijkatlas five months to receive all relevant datasets for their first project).
- Not all indicators displayed in the OBI swing-viewer are up-to-date (sometimes just placeholders instead of actual data).
- Similar to the Antwerp situation: although data is all available online, city officials experience difficulties in finding the information they need, which creates extra workload for OBI, the health monitor, and many of the cross-departmental interactions.
- Privacy is, here as well, an issue experienced by the interviewees. A general Data Protection Impact Assessment is being drafted to address exchange of datasets among city departments but has proven difficult to get into practice.

2.6.4. Recommendations

- A quick win is to structurally improve data sharing regarding the Wijkatlas. The work done in this framework is critical, as it tries to combine different policy objectives before actually starting a project. General implementation can save the city much budget, and the metrics calculated (green area / inhabitant, ...) can be generalized across all districts of Rotterdam, given access to the data.
- A second recommendation, especially to cut costs and free up valuable time for the researchers, is checking whether data can be centralized into one ADF / Swingviewer subscription, as we already know of at least two separate, the same, paid plans. This can improve data availability, as more information is centralized in one, freely accessible platform, and can help improve keeping the included datasets up-to-date. All elements seem to be present, though a structured approach from management is needed to make this happen.
- Questionnaires and surveys: Coordinating efforts in questions to ask and contacting respondents can mitigate survey fatigue.

